

Whole-genome sequence of *Paenibacillus polymyxa* strain 77b with biocontrol potential against the bacterial phytopathogen *Agrobacterium tumefaciens*

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Abstract

This study reports the complete and annotated genome assemblies of a rhizosphere strain *Paenibacillus polymyxa* 77b. This strain exhibits potent antibacterial activity against *Agrobacterium tumefaciens* strains C58 and B6 both *in vitro* and in tomato plants. Whole Genome Sequencing (WGS) was used for an in-depth understanding of strain 77b and to gain insights into its potential for its application in the fields of agriculture as a biocontrol bacterium.

Introduction

Agrobacterium tumefaciens poses a significant threat to various plants species of dicotyledonous plants from almost 100 different families by inducing crown gall tumors (De Cleene and De Ley, 1976; Escobar and Dandekar, 2003). These tumors cause substantial annual losses in agricultural production, particularly in nurseries and orchards (Ben Abdallah et al., 2015; Frikha-Gargouri et al., 2017). In Tunisia, crown gall is currently a major handicap for the production of plants, in particular stone fruit trees (Ben Abdallah et al., 2015; Zouba and Hammami, 1988). Despite the great efforts deployed, controlling crown gall disease remains a challenging task (Kuzmanović et al., 2018). Many strategies were used to manage crown gall disease including chemicals, soil solarization, and soil amendments (Gupta and Kamal, 2006; Moore et al., 1996; Tolba and Soliman, 2013). Among these treatments, chemical pesticides have been a subject of public concern due to their negative environmental impact, their

phytotoxicity, and their potential health risk related to the emergence of resistant pathogens (Alengebawy et al., 2021; Waard et al., 1993).

In recent years, a trend in utilizing microorganisms as biopesticides has emerged. Microbial biopesticides, particularly those from *Bacillus*, *Agrobacterium*, *Pseudomonas*, and *Paenibacillus* genera, offer effective and eco-friendly alternatives (Archana et al., 2022; Elnahal et al., 2022; Hussain et al., 2020; Thakur et al., 2020; Yousfi et al., 2024). Particularly, *Paenibacillus* species such as *Paenibacillus polymyxa* are known for their wide habitat range and ability to produce antimicrobial compounds (Daud et al., 2019; Grady et al., 2016; Yuan et al., 2023). These strains exhibit multiple mechanisms of action including antibiosis and plant growth promotion (Daud et al., 2019; Grady et al., 2016; Langendries and Goormachtig, 2021; Rybakova et al., 2016; Saisai and Jingze, 2019).

In recent years, the rapid development of sequencing technology proved to be a promising approach to characterize the genetic traits involved in plant beneficial functions including biocontrol and plant growth promotion potentialities; and gain insights into the molecular mechanisms underlying these complex biological processes. Only few genomes of *P. polymyxa* strains were previously sequenced and studied for their mechanism of biocontrol and/or plant growth promotion at the molecular level such as strain HY96-2 (Luo et al., 2018) and PJH16 (Yang et al., 2024).

A rhizospheric strain named *P. polymyxa* 77b was previously selected for its broad range of antimicrobial activities, particularly its antibacterial activity against *A. tumefaciens* strains C58 and B6 (data not shown). To provide some insight into its biocontrol mechanisms, the genome of strain *P. polymyxa* 77b was completely sequenced.

Material and Methods

Bacterial isolates

P. polymyxa strain 77b was isolated from a rhizospheric soil in Sfax, Tunisia.

Sequencing of bacterial genomic DNA

Bacteria were prepared following MicrobesNG strain submission procedures. MicrobesNG performed DNA processing. DNA quantification and library preparation were conducted on a Hamilton Microlab STAR automated liquid handling system (Hamilton Bonaduz AG, Switzerland). Genomic DNA libraries were prepared using the Nextera XT Library Prep Kit (Illumina, San Diego, USA) following the manufacturer's protocol with some modifications:

the amount of input DNA was increased 2-fold, and the PCR elongation time was increased to 45 seconds. Libraries were sequenced on an Illumina NovaSeq 6000 (Illumina, San Diego, USA) using a 250 bp paired-end protocol.

The reads were adapter trimmed using Trimmomatic version 0.30 (Bolger et al., 2014) with a sliding window quality cutoff of Q15. *De novo* assembly was performed on samples using SPAdes version 3.7 (Bankevich et al., 2012), and contigs were annotated using Prokka 1.11 (Seemann, 2014).

Results

Genomic Features

A summary of the genomic features for *P. polymyxa* strain 77b is listed in table 1. Genome assembly leads to 6.4 Mb with $165.554 \times$ mean coverage. The number of protein coding genes was 5632 genes and the G + C content was 44.84 %. The strain harbors 114 tRNA and only one tmRNA (Table1).

Nucleotides sequences accession numbers

The *P. polymyxa* strain 77b complete genome sequence has been deposited in the NCBI GenBank under accession numbers listed in table 1.

Table1: Genomic features of *P. polymyxa* strain 77b

Bacterial species	<i>P. polymyxa</i>
Strain	77b
Genome size (bp)	6350379
% GC	44.84
Number of contigs (>=1000 bp)	33
Largest contig (bp)	1547173
Mean coverage (X)	165.554
Number of reads	2167908
N50 (bp)	406425
Protein-coding gene	5632
tRNA number	114
tmRNA number	1
SRA accession numbers	SRR28335520
Assemblies accession numbers	GCA_037415035.1

Statement on continuing work

The datasets are being made available before their formal publication and should be considered as preliminary. We welcome feedback from the community. For further information, please contact OFG (olfafrikhagargouri2@gmail.com).

Acknowledgements

The sequencing of the bacterial strains was supported by the GetGenome initiative of The Sainsbury Laboratory, Norwich, UK, with support from the Gatsby Charitable Foundation and the Biotechnology and Biological Sciences Research Council (BBBSRC). We would like to thank Prof. Sophien Kamoun, Dr. James Canham and Dr. Joe Win for their valuable assistance.

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